

Effect of Emitted Gases on the Health of Workers in the Oil Sector

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Abstract:

This study was conducted on a group of oil refinery workers. The aim of this research is to reveal the extent to which workers in this field are exposed to types of pollution, including pollution resulting from toxic gases during works as well as health problems to which they may be exposed. This study showed higher urea and creatinine levels in some workers compared to the control sample there was a slight increase in blond images, as well as an increase in the content of liver enzyme and alkaline phosphates. Therefore, proper and correct preventive methods must be followed to avoid problems

resulting from working in this field.

Keywords: *environmental pollution, oil sector, workers' health, professional diseases.*

Introduction

Crude oil production operations in Iraq were accompanied by huge quantities of associated gas, most of which are burned, which led to very large oil and gas residues that contributed significantly to environmental pollution and damage to the quality of life of Iraqi people in light of the absence of legal legislation that limits environmental pollution in Iraq.

Environmental pollution can be defined as contamination of the chemical, physical and biological components of the earth and atmosphere system to the extent that they negatively affect normal environmental

processes. Polluted work environment places are of great importance to the health of workers, especially in the oil sector, and therefore many diseases and health problems can occur mainly as a result of practicing incorrect practical behaviors such as burning ineffective materials, direct disposal of waste in the work environment, and exposure to leakage of emitted gases.

Inhalation of certain gases triggers an allergic response that leads to inflammation and, in some cases, respiratory tract infection. Inhaled gases can cause general body poisoning (including difficulty breathing) because they are toxic to

body cells, or because they displace oxygen in the blood and thus limit the amount of oxygen that reaches tissues (such as methane or carbon monoxide). For some people, breathing in small amounts of gas or other chemicals over a long period may lead to chronic bronchitis (inflammation of the airways).

Many important problems have emerged in the field of environmental pollution and various environmental elements, as scientific progress has been accompanied by the emergence of many chemical compounds harmful to the environment. Such as the gases resulting from fuel combustion and various industrial activities, which included many toxic compounds, the most important of which are carbon monoxide and methane, which resulted in air pollution around us.

A person may be patient with hunger for several weeks and thirst for days, but he does not tolerate the lack of air or its corruption for more than a few minutes. Therefore, preserving the environment in the oil sector and others is one of the most important strategies and goals that we seek at the present time, which called on many countries of the world to enact legislation and laws that help protect the environment from pollution, and because the world is moving forward in the field of oil development, so it has become necessary take the appropriate decisions that lead to preserving the environment from the dangers of pollution in order to protect workers in the oil sector.

The aim of this research is to make a comparison between individuals who are not working in the oil sector and individuals working in the oil sector by conducting a blood picture and examinations of the liver and kidneys.

Materials and Methods

Collecting Blood Samples

Blood samples were collected randomly from two groups:

- The first group: It includes healthy samples from non-workers in the oil sector.

- The second group: includes samples of workers in the oil sector.

Blood was drawn from the two sets of tubes containing anticoagulant (EDTA) for the purpose of measuring the blood picture (CBC) and other tubes of the type (Gel tube) for the purpose of separating blood serum, which is a liquid dissolved in the blood that does not play a role in the coagulation process. It is blood plasma without fibrinogens for the purpose of conducting biochemical tests, where approximately 3 ml of blood was placed in it, and then centrifuged using a centrifuge at a speed of 3000 revolutions / min for 15 minutes to obtain blood serum that was preserved by freezing in the refrigerator at a temperature (-20C°) and until the biochemical tests required to be conducted in the biochemistry laboratory.

Assessment of the Blood Picture

Complete blood picture examinations (CBC) were performed using the Complete blood count, which is an analyzer device with an automatic multi-scale system and important for diagnostic blood tests in clinical laboratories, where 0.5 ml of blood was taken and placed in EDTA tubes to prevent clotting, and the tube was shaken well. The blood image examinations included RBC, WBCs, HB, Lym and PLT, as the examinations were carried out according to the method of work by the Korean company (NIPICON).

Estimation of Renal Function

- Creatinine Estimation:

Creatinine was estimated using the ready-made kit (kit) manufactured by the French BIOLABO company, where it was worked according to the working method installed on the ready-made kit, and the absorption intensity was read on the spectrophotometer at (492) nm, and the concentration of creatinine was calculated using the equation the following:

Creatinine concentration (mg/dl).

Absorbance of the sample/absorbance of the standard solution × concentration of the standard solution

- Estimation of urea:

Urea was estimated using the ready-made kit (kit) manufactured by the French company (BIOLABO), and the work was done according to the working method installed on the readymade kit. The absorption intensity was read on the spectrophotometer at (600) nanometers, and the urea concentration was calculated using the equation the following:

Urea concentration (mg/dl).

Absorbance of the sample/absorbance of the standard solution × concentration of the standard solution

- Estimation of liver function (GOT and GPT):

The urea was estimated using the ready-made kit (kit) manufactured by the French company ((BIOLABO) and the work was done according to the working method installed on the ready-made kit, and the absorption intensity was read on the spectrophotometer at (600) nm wavelength, and the urea concentration was calculated using the equation the following:

Creatinine concentration (mg/dl).

Absorbance of the sample/absorbance of the standard solution × concentration of the standard solution

Results and Discussion

Both figures 1 and 2 showed the results of kidney function for a control sample and field workers in the oil sector, who are most exposed to gases (hydrogen sulfide, methane and carbon monoxide). It was noted that the level of urea and creatinine increased in the blood of workers in the oil sector for each compared to the control group (healthy).), This may be due to a decrease in renal filtration rates due to frequent and continuous exposure to those emitted gases, which enter the body in several ways, such as inhalation and absorption through the skin, which leads to a decrease in the glomerular filtration rate of the kidneys, in addition to the damage that occurs to the structure of the kidney nephrons, which leads to This leads to a decrease in the activity and function of the kidneys (Uhegbu Imo, 2015).

We note in samples No. (1) and No. (2) where all creatinine and urea levels were close to the (healthy) control sample, perhaps due to their following special health instructions by wearing masks and protective gloves during work, and continuous sterilization after completing work. In addition to not taking medications and drugs that affect the function and work of the kidneys.

Figure 1. The Results of Urea for Control Sample and Workers in the Oil Sector

Figure 2. The Results of Creatinine for a Control Sample and Workers in the Oil Sector

Figure (3) shows effect of emitted gases on levels of blood images of a control sample and field workers in the oil sector, where the results indicated a variation in platelet counts (PLT) in samples of field workers in the oil sector, due to their continuous exposure to emitted gases and their entry into the body through inhalation, ingestion or absorption, which leads to a discrepancy in blood components, as its effect lies on lymphocytes (lymph%) and thus makes workers vulnerable to various diseases, which may become chronic over time.

It is also noted through figure (3) that the rest of the image of blood components did not show a

significant difference compared to the healthy eye, and it may be due to the workers' commitment to health conditions or to the small number of workers working in this oil sector, which led to the absence of a significant difference between the blood components of the workers. ; Or perhaps age has a role in that, as workers of young ages may have less harm when exposed to these emitted gases. But with the accumulation of continuous work, continuous exposure, and advancing age, greater damage occurs due to the leakage of emitted gases (Nicholson, 2016).

Figure 3. The Results of the Levels of Blood Images of the Control Sample and Workers in the Oil Sector

Figure (4) shows an uneven rise in the percentages of GOT, GPT, and ALP in the samples of field workers assigned to work in the oil sector, compared to the (healthy) control group. This is due to their constant exposure to the gases emitted from them and their entry into the body through inhalation, ingestion, or

absorption, which leads to an increase in the components of GOT, GPT, and ALP, and this leads to a decrease in the effectiveness of the human immune system, as it becomes susceptible to various diseases, some of which may become chronically over time (Nicholson, 2011).

Figure 4. Percentages of GOT, GPT, and ALP in Samples of Workers in the Oil Sector

Conclusions

There was a rise in urea and creatinine in some samples of workers in the oil sector compared to the (healthy) control group.

There were noticed slight and varying increases in the blood image of workers in the oil sector, compared to the (healthy) control group.

There was a slight increase in liver enzymes and alkaline phosphatase in the samples of workers in the oil sector, compared to the (healthy) control group.

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